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**Finding Endometriosis using Machine Learning
FEMaLe**

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1.5	02-07-2024	Final version ready for submission, quality checked by FEMaLe PMO.	AU	Validated

¹ As per the project's cloud storage or per email date if applicable.

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Legislation

Legislation H2020 Framework Programme – Regulation (EU) No 1291/2013 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 December 2013 establishing Horizon 2020 – The Framework Programme for Research and Innovation (2014-2020) (OJ 347, 20.12.2013, p. 104).

Euratom Research and Training Programme (2014-2018) – Council Regulation (Euratom) No 1314/2013 of 16 December 2013 on the Research and Training Programme of the European Atomic Energy Community (2014-2018) complementing the Horizon 2020 – The Framework Programme for Research and Innovation (OJ L 347, 20.12.2013, p. 948).

H2020 Specific Programme – Council Decision 2013/743/EU of 3 December 2013 establishing the Specific Programme Implementing Horizon 2020 – The Framework Programme for Research and Innovation (2014-2020) (OJ L 347, 20.12.2013, p. 965).

Rules for Participation (RfP) – Regulation (EU) No 1290/2013 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 of December 2013 laying down the rules for the participation and dissemination in Horizon 2020 – the Framework Programme for Research and Innovation (2014-2020) (OJ L 347, 20.12.2013, p.81).

Financial Regulation (FR) – Regulation (EC, Euratom) No 966/2012 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 25 October 2012 on the financial rules applicable to the general budget of the European Union (OJ L 298, 26.10.2012, p.1).

Rules of Application (RAP) – Commission Regulation (EC, Euratom) No 1268/2012 of 29 October 2012 on the rules of application of 1 Regulation (EC, Euratom) No 966/2012 of the European Parliament and of the Council on the financial rules applicable to the general budget of the Union (OJ L 298, 26.10.2012, p.1).

1. Process of developing the Lucy App MY-ENDO module

Our goal in FEMaLe Project's Delivery 8.3 is to reach the widest possible audience with MY-ENDO. To do this, we decided to make the program available to users of the Lucy app.

During FEMaLe project, two versions of MY-ENDO were developed. One is a research platform that meets strict security and privacy requirements, hosted at Aarhus University, and the other is a WordPress-based solution that does not contain any personal data, enabling upscaling and implementation.

By modifying the latter version, we have made it possible for anyone to register and take advantage of the programme. The main focus is on psychoeducation, with hundreds of pages of useful information on endometriosis and ways to cope.

During the development of the WordPress-based version, we paid special attention to responsive UI design, so that the content would display properly on desktop PCs as well as on tablets and phones. This made it easy to integrate the MY-ENDO WebApp into *Lucy App*.

We also integrated the Translatepress module into the WordPress software, which made it really easy to add translations to the existing solution created during Delivery 8.2. As a result, the MY-ENDO program is now available in Danish, English and Hungarian for *Lucy App* users already.

Users can now simply access a MY-ENDO menu item in the 'Knowledge Base' in the *Lucy App*, with a short summary and a button to directly open the WordPress application.

The user of the MY-ENDO application and the user of the Lucy application are treated as separate entities, so no unwanted data leakage can occur and no data connection is made between the two applications. The user registration used for MY-ENDO is used solely to allow the software to save progress and the user to continue the program either on a desktop computer or on a tablet outside of *Lucy App*.

2. Screen shots of the software

What is this?

MY-ENDO is an awareness and acceptance-based treatment programme designed to help you better manage the negative physical, psychological and social symptoms and consequences of endometriosis.

How can you use the program?

- MyEndo program
Program link

Mi ez?

A MY-ENDO egy tudatosságon és elfogadáson alapuló kezelési program, amelynek célja, hogy segítsen jobban kezelni az endometriózis negatív fizikai, pszichológiai és szociális tüneteit és következményeit.

Hogyan használhatod a programot?

- MyEndo program
Program link

Introduktion

Velkommen til behandlingsprogrammet MY-ENDO – ”Mind Your ENDOMetriosis”.

MY-ENDO er et mindfulness- og acceptbaseret behandlingsforløb, som har til formål at hjælpe dig til bedre at kunne håndtere af de fysiske, psykiske og sociale symptomer og følgevirkninger, du oplever ved sygdommen endometriose.

Vi vil her starte med at give dig en

recommend that you listen to and practice the exercise on a daily basis during the first week.

Have a great time!

LINK: Body scan - long (audio file)

Back to Lesson

Introduction to the "Calm" exercises:

Yoga video 8 (A): Savasana

Yoga video 8 (B): Savasana on a ball

Yoga video 16: The Cat

16:35
program.myendo.dk

^ Collapse All

About the MY-ENDO treatment program
5 Topics
^ Collapse

 Lesson Content
0% COMPLETE | 0/5 Steps

About MY-ENDO

The experiences with MY-ENDO

The content of the program

Implementation in everyday life

Your time is the most important investment

16:35
program.myendo.dk

There will be text material for you to immerse yourself in, and there will be various guided exercises both as audio files and videos. In addition, there will be some worksheets for you to complete. You can download and print the complete booklet with worksheets here (LINK).

The structure of the program entails more reading and listening in the first four weeks of the program. As the weeks progress, there will be less reading and more everyday practicing for you to finally implement the new good habits in your everyday life.

Mark Complete ✓

Back to Lesson

Start: INTRODUCTION > About the MY-...

IN PROGRESS

LESSON PROGRESS
100% COMPLETE

Lesson Content

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- About MY-ENDO
- The experiences with MY-ENDO
- The content of the program
- Implementation in everyday life
- Your time is the most important investment

IN PROGRESS

LESSON PROGRESS
0% COMPLETE

Lesson Content

0% COMPLETE | 0/3 Steps

- Mindfulness exercise: Body scan
- What do you notice? (worksheet)
- Mindful yoga exercises

